

Perception of Helicopter Parenting and Mental Health Outcomes in College Students: A Correlational Study

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There are distinct styles of parenting, and Helicopter parenting is one of them, where parents involve themselves in a developmentally inappropriate way and try to control the life of their child, which is evident through their advice, assistance to the child and monitoring the life of the child. Therefore, there is a further need to examine the effects of perception of Helicopter Parenting on college-going students. The present study attempts to examine the impact of Parental hovering on Anxiety and Depression in College students. The sample consisted of 300 college-going students (150 males & 150 females) in the age range of 18-21 years from co-educational colleges of the University of Delhi. To assess the perception of Helicopter Parenting, Helicopter Parenting Scale (LeMoyne & Buchanan, 2011) was utilised, and to measure the Anxiety and Depression, Anxiety, Depression and Stress Scale (Bhatnagar et al., 2011) was utilised. The data was analysed using the correlation analysis. Descriptive statistics consisting of mean and standard deviation, were also used. The results posit a positive relationship between perception of Helicopter Parenting (Both Mother & Father) and Anxiety ($p < .01$) and Depression ($p < .01$). These results could be utilized heuristically to understand the impact of Helicopter Parenting on students Anxiety and Depression level.

Keywords: Helicopter parenting, anxiety, depression, over-involvement

The relationship between parent and child is very crucial and paramount in the life of the child. Many researchers focus on the parenting styles from the parents' perception but understanding the parenting styles adopted by parents from the child's perception is even a better way to look into any child's behaviour. Initially, the term Helicopter Parenting was used as a metaphor to express the over-involvement of mothers' in the life of a child (Ginott, 1969) later it was used by Cline and Fay (1990) in their famous book series '*Parenting with love and logic*', they tried explaining the hovering of the parents and stated they behave like this as "they confuse love, protection, and caring" by trying to act as a shield and protect the child from any failure in their life (Odenweller et al., 2014). Helicopter Parents are in constant touch with their child, interfere in the daily affairs of the child, and tend to over involve and over protect by removing all the hurdles in their child's life. These parents try to make all the decisions in their child's life and invest personally in future goals of the child (LeMoyne & Buchanan, 2011; Padilla-Walker & Nelson, 2012; Segrin et al., 2012).

Reasons why do Parents Over-involve?

Rationales parents give for over-involving (Daitch, 2017)

- Parents are apprehensive about the stressful outcomes in the life of

their child and how their child will manage on their own.

- They feel anxious about day-to-day crises like job placements and the economy, and they try to control their child's life in a way to protect them.
- They try to overcompensate for their own childhood by being overly involved in their child's life.
- Pressure from other parents, who are already hovering.

A study was conducted by Ulutas and Aksoy (2014) to investigate the relationship between the hovering of parents and social connectedness and the level of anxiety in a sample of 422 college-going students, and the results posit that hovering of parents increased the anxiety of these college-going students. Similarly, Montgomery (2010) examined the impact of hovering of parents on undergraduate students with a sample of 300 students. The results posit that students who reported over-involvement of parents were high on anxiety. On the contrary, Gastel et al. (2009) results revealed that perception of Helicopter Parenting by their child was negatively related with the child's Anxiety level. Whereas, Beato et al. (2015) results indicated that over-involvement of parents and the level of anxiety of their children are not significantly related.

Studies have been done to investigate the relationship between over-involvement of parents and Depression as well. Pautler (2017) conducted a study with a sample of 87 University students to examine the relationship between over-involvement of parents and Worry, Depression, Self-Efficacy in terms of Academic Achievement. The results posit that those students who perceived their parents as Helicopter Parents were high on Worry and Depression. Darlow et al. (2017) investigated the impact of Hovering of Parents on Depressive symptoms, Self-efficacy, Anxious symptoms and college adjustment on college students with a sample of 294 students. The results revealed that there is a positive relationship between Helicopter Parenting and Depression and

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Anxiety. Whereas Fröjd et al. (2007) results revealed that over-involvement of parents was negatively linked with the depressive and anxious symptoms of adolescents.

Parents play an irreplaceable role in the life of their child. In some instances, however, the parents become overly-involved in the lives of their children. Consequently, this type of parenting where parents are exerting excess control on child and are monitoring every move can lead to lifelong psychological damage to the child (Br et al., 2019). On the contrary, literature posits that Helicopter Parenting facilitates development which is healthy in nature and pro-social behaviour in adolescents (Combs-Orme et al., 2003; Day & Padilla-Walker, 2009; Joussemet et al., 2008; Pomerantz et al., 2007). Therefore, this topic needs further research so as to gain a better understanding of this concept, which can have constructive implications for parents, teachers and educational counsellors.

Statement of the Problem

The present study aims to examine the impact of the perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father) on Anxiety and Depression of the college students.

Objectives of the Study

The present research has been designed keeping in mind the following objectives:

To study the relationship of perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father) with Anxiety and Depression among college students.

Hypotheses of the Study

- H.1. Perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father) is expected to be positively related to Anxiety among college students
- H.2. Perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father) is expected to be positively related to Depression among college students

Method

Participants

The sample consisted of 300 college students, including 150 males and 150 females, aged 18 to 21 years. Participants were selected from co-educational colleges affiliated with the University of Delhi. Specifically, 10 colleges were randomly chosen from a total of 91 colleges. Data was collected from these colleges using purposive sampling.

Measures

Brief Description of Tests: Helicopter Parenting Scale (HPS; LeMoyne & Buchanan, 2011): The test comprised of 8 items associated with the perception of child for the over-involvement of the parents. To each item participants can respond on a scale from 1 (*totally disagree*) to 6 (*totally agree*). For calculating the total score add each item's score and divide it by 8 (*total items in the scale*). The higher the score it represents higher level of perception of Helicopter Parenting by the respondent. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for reliability was calculated as 0.71 (LeMoyne & Buchanan, 2011).

Anxiety, Depression and Stress Scale (Bhatnagar et al., 2011): The scale comprised of 48 items with 3 subscales-Anxiety (19 items), Depression (15 items) and Stress (14 items). This scale can be

administered by self or the examiner. Participants need to respond in 'Yes' or 'No'. For scoring purpose, score of 1 is given if the response is 'Yes' and 0 if the response is 'No'. The score ranges from 0-19 for Anxiety, 0-15 for Depression and 0-14 for Stress. High scores by the participants indicate that the person is experiencing high level of Anxiety, Depression and Stress and vice-versa. In terms of internal consistency as measured by Cronbach's Alpha and Spearman-Brown coefficient, the reliability of the total scale is 0.81 and 0.89.

Statistical Analysis

Keeping in view the objectives and the hypotheses of the study, correlation analysis was used. Descriptive statistics consisting of mean and standard deviation was also used.

Procedure

The testing schedule was conducted personally. The subjects were given the questionnaire booklet and were requested to respond to it truthfully. Participants were assured that their results and the information obtained from them and it would be kept completely confidential; and will be used for research purposes only. The participants were provided with basic instructions for each test, and clarification of doubts was provided, whenever needed.

Results and Discussion

Table 1.1

Inter Correlation Matrix for Perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father), Anxiety and Depression

Variables	1	2	3	4
Helicopter Parenting (mother)	1	.737**	.604**	.568**
Helicopter Parenting (father)		1	.530**	.548**
Anxiety			1	.718**
Depression				1

Note. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 1.2

Inter Correlation Matrix for Perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father) of male Students, Anxiety and Depression

Variables	1	2	3	4
Helicopter Parenting (mother)	1	.784**	.620**	.583**
Helicopter Parenting (father)		1	.502**	.541**
Anxiety			1	.752**
Depression				1

Note. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 1.3

Inter Correlation Matrix for Perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father) of Female Students, Anxiety and Depression

Variables	1	2	3	4
Helicopter Parenting (mother)	1	.698**	.590**	.556**
Helicopter Parenting (father)		1	.560**	.556**
Anxiety			1	.684**
Depression				1

Note. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 2

Showing Mean and S.D of Perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father), Anxiety and Depression (N=300)

S.no	Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Perception of Helicopter parenting (Mother)	3.28	0.67
2	Perception of Helicopter parenting (Father)	3.26	0.66
3	Anxiety	7.33	4.50
4	Depression	5.72	3.96

The present study attempted to examine the perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father) and its impact on Anxiety and Depression of the college going students. Table 1.1 shows the intercorrelational matrices for the total sample and results revealed that for the perception of Helicopter Parenting of mother was positively and significantly related with anxiety ($p < .01$) and depression ($p < .01$). Similarly, results revealed that perception of Helicopter Parenting of father was positively and significantly related with anxiety ($p < .01$) and depression ($p < .01$). Results also revealed that perception of Helicopter Parenting of mother was positively and significantly related with perception of Helicopter Parenting of father ($p < .01$).

Table 1.2 shows the intercorrelational matrices for the male sample and results revealed that for the perception of Helicopter Parenting of mother was positively and significantly related with anxiety ($p < .01$) and depression ($p < .01$). Similarly, results revealed that perception of Helicopter Parenting of father was positively and significantly related with anxiety ($p < .01$) and depression ($p < .01$). Results also revealed that perception of Helicopter Parenting of mother was positively and significantly related with perception of Helicopter Parenting of father ($p < .01$).

Table 1.3 shows the intercorrelational matrices for the female sample and results revealed that for the perception of Helicopter Parenting of mother was positively and significantly related with anxiety ($p < .01$) and depression ($p < .01$). Similarly, results revealed that perception of Helicopter Parenting of father was positively and significantly related with anxiety ($p < .01$) and depression ($p < .01$). Results also revealed that perception of Helicopter Parenting of mother was positively and significantly related with perception of Helicopter Parenting of father ($p < .01$).

Table 2 shows the means and standard deviations of each variable. The mean of perception of Helicopter Parenting of mother was 3.28 and 3.26 for female, the mean of perception of Helicopter Parenting of father was 3.25 and 3.26 for female, the mean of Well-Being was 40.10 for male and 40.11 for female and the mean of Life Satisfaction was 23.77 for male and 26.50 for female. Overall, the means of variables depicts moderate level of perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother & Father).

Cline and Fay (2020) stated that the children of Helicopter Parents become totally dependent on being given instructions to follow and reinforcement. To examine the impact of hovering of parents on pre-school children Edwards et al. (2010) conducted research with a sample of 632 mothers and 249 fathers. The results of the study posit that as the hovering of parents increased, the level of Anxiety also increased among the children. In another study by Hong and Cui (2020) to investigate the effects of Helicopter parenting and the Anxiety level in college-going students with a sample of 432 students, results revealed that Helicopter Parenting was positively related with the Anxiety level of these college-going students.

Similarly, Borelli et al. (2014) examined the association between Helicopter Parenting and Anxiety with a sample of 102 school going adolescents. The results of the study posit that students with Helicopter parenting reported high on Anxiety. Van Der Bruggen et al. (2008) in their study investigated the relation between control by parents and Anxiety in these children. Sample of 1305 parent-child dyads were taken. Results of the investigation revealed that those children of those parents who over-involved reported high on Anxiety symptoms. Klein and Pierce (2009) in their study examined the relation between Hovering of Parents and Anxiety of college going students. The results of the study revealed that those students who reported over-involvement of parents were high on Anxiety symptoms. A study was conducted by Fulton et al. (2014) to investigate the perception of Helicopter Parenting and Anxiety in young adults with a sample of 380 individuals with the age range of 18-42 years (average age 20.23). The results of the study revealed that perceived Hovering of Parents was positively related with the Anxiety level of these young adults. A similar study was conducted by Cui et al. (2018) to investigate the relation between Over-involvement of Parents and the young adults' problems related with the Well-Being with the sample of 441 American University Students and 306 Finnish University Students. The results posits that those students who reported Over-involvement of Parents were high on Anxiety, Depressive Symptoms, Dissatisfied with Life and dysregulation in Emotions.

Studies in the area of perception of Helicopter Parenting (Mother and Father) have reported positive relationship with Depression. Moilane and Manuel (2019) investigated the link between Helicopter Parenting and adjustment related results (Social Competency, Pro-Social Behaviour, Depressive Symptoms, Substance Use & Criminal ideation). Sample of 302 individuals with the age range of 18-24 years were taken. The results revealed that Hovering of Parents was related with low level of Self-Regulating behaviour, Mastery, Social Competency and high level of Depressive Symptoms. Reilly and Semkovska (2018) conducted a study to examine the impact of Over-involvement of parents on Depression level of college going students with a sample of 208 students. The results of the study posit that Over-involvement of Parents was positively related with Depression in these students. Other researchers (Barber & Harmon, 2002; Soenens et al., 2004) also posit similar findings, students with Helicopter Parenting reported high on Depression. Similarly, Wenzel et al. (2019) conducted a study to investigate the Hovering of Parents and its results on college going students with a sample of 104 students from U.S. Results posit that Hovering of Parents resulted in high level of Depression in students. Cook (2020) examined the role of Over-involvement of the parents and college-going students Competence in Relations (Friendship & Romantic Relationship), Substance Abuse and Depression with a sample of 637 college-going students of the United States. Results of the study revealed that Over-involvement of parents was positively related to Depression, Substance Abuse, and low level of Relationship Competency. Additionally, Schiffrin et al. (2013) conducted research to investigate the role of Self-Determination Theory in examining the association between Helicopter Parenting and Depressive symptoms in college-going students with a sample of 297. The results point towards a positive relationship between Helicopter Parenting and Depression in college students. Colder et al. (1997) attempted to explore the relationship between the parenting style

adopted by parents and its impact on Aggression and Depression among school going boys with a sample of 64 grade fourth and fifth students. Results revealed that boys who reported high level of parental involvement also reported high on Depression.

Conclusion and Implications of the Study

The young adults of the present as well as future generation are indeed facing enormous challenges, emotionally, physically, developmentally and so on. These challenges, mostly emanating as a result of multiple factors, as one of them is parenting style. The present investigation specifically addressed the rise of Helicopter Parenting as a Parenting Style adopted by parents, which is also found to be holding significant negative results on college-going students' Anxiety and Depression. In light of the above, the present investigation vehemently highlights need for proper guidance and counselling sessions, which aims at helping these students overcome the negative impacts of Hovering of Parents as well as creating some programs for the parents to make them understand the effective parenting style and its effect on their child.

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